

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract

Problems related to teaching foreign languages the article deals with the importance of teaching Deutsch as a foreign language in our modern life, at the same time it mentions the problems or difficulties appearing while teaching a foreign language. Any foreign language is taught on the aim of giving opportunities to speak and understand in this language. Speaking a foreign language doesn't only mean producing words, expressions, but also it means to enable the students to pronounce the words correctly, to make up proper grammatical and lexical sentences. During the teaching process teachers usually observe numerous different problems that prevent the learners from fluent speech and correct understanding.

Keywords: language skills, reading, speaking, listening, speech, foreign language

In modern times, special attention is paid to the teaching of foreign languages, mainly German, and all ways, methods and methodologies that will bring success in teaching are thoroughly investigated. Although modern methodological science offers countless methods to teachers and students, problems that need to be solved often arise in this field. Experienced and very good teachers have gained their experience and knowledge not based on theories, but based on their activities in the classroom. In theory, being very literate does not necessarily mean being a very good teacher. As we know, foreign language teaching faces such a question: what to teach, how and why to teach that material. Every teacher who starts teaching must also determine whether the course he/she gives answers these questions. In modern times, the teaching of any foreign language mainly involves two requirements:

- 1) to express one's opinion in a foreign language;
- 2) understand speech in a foreign language.

Putting forward these demands once again proves that the success to be achieved in teaching foreign languages is mainly related to the methodology. A teacher's performance needs to be based on facts, and there are many different ways to discover these facts. Examples of these include:

- 1) making audio or video recordings of lessons;
- 2) to present a questionnaire to students;
- 3) conducting interviews with students;
- 4) invite colleagues or at least one of them to listen to the lesson.

One of the most important factors for a perfect lesson is what the teacher sets. The goal is that the teacher organizes the lesson based on it. In the book "Teaching Foreign Language Skills" written by Wilga Rivers, learners are put into four groups to see how the same material is taught by several experienced teachers, and in each group they encounter a completely different lesson. After the lessons are over, each of the teachers explains the goal he has set for this lesson. Therefore, the fact that the goals are different from each other is related to the variety of lesson types. I have been teaching German at the University for a long time, and over the years I have tried to find out the reasons

for the difficulties that students face in the process of learning the language. Students face certain difficulties in each of the four main factors of foreign language learning (writing, reading, listening comprehension and speaking) and of course an experienced teacher is the most important help to overcome these problems.

I wanted to write this article not about the general situation, but specifically taking into account the problems of the students in the groups I teach this language at Nakhchivan State University. I think the main problem for our students is that they get used to the German language, which has a different structure from our mother tongue, rather slowly and with difficulty. It is not very difficult to solve the problems in writing. For this, teachers use many types of writing tasks and assignment forms in class and at home. Among such tasks, the most common methods include face copying, reading carefully, spelling, answering questions, giving a written description of a given picture. The main reason for difficulties in reading is that the letters and sounds of words in German, which is different from our language, are distinctive. The absence of letters in the alphabet for some sounds, the combination of letters creating different sounds, and in some cases the unpronounceability of several letters also create problems.

Taking this problem seriously, repeating the same material many times does not lead to a better understanding of the students. Language, which is the main means of communication, is mainly understood through conversation, so the main goal of teaching foreign languages is for students to have the ability to use this language in a practical way. In order to create a language environment for our students, a lot of work has been done at the university, computer rooms, electronic boards allow students to listen to materials in the taught language, watch movies, record their own conversations and then listen to them many times, and find out their mistakes. I summarize the main problem for students to speak with two facts:

- 1) Azerbaijani and German languages have a different structure and difficulty in pronouncing some necessary words;

2) Organization of psychological conditions that create students' desire and need to speak. (They should feel the need to inform, explain, ask and prove something about someone or something so that they are eager to talk).

I would consider the second point to be the main cause of difficulty, because usually when I ask students to make up a dialogue or a small story and tell it, they think quietly for a long time and always complain that they can't think of a good idea. While the teachers help them to find topics and answers, while saying sentences in Azerbaijani, students can easily translate and create dialogues and situations. In order to develop students' speaking ability, to make it fast and fluent, the teacher must be able to listen and explain patiently, and in the initial stages, stopping the student often for mistakes is very harmful for his speech, because then the student will be shy to speak and forget the ideas he will speak. Babayev Javid underlines in his article: "Speaking skill forms as a result of listening process while writing skill formalizes as a result of reading process" [1, p. 7].

For fluent and fast speech, it is not only important to have a lot of vocabulary, to be able to pronounce them correctly, students also need to participate in a situation that can quickly create a language environment, and most importantly, it is not possible to read correctly without thinking in a foreign language. Just as the vocabulary of many world languages has benefited from the German language, the German language has been enriched by other languages and continues to be enriched even now. Words that have been transferred from these foreign languages often do not obey the pronunciation rules of German, maintaining the pronunciation that corresponds to their origin. Therefore, the pronunciation of words that are difficult to pronounce or that are exceptional should be taught to students through repetition and listening in such a way that they can read these words immediately, without thinking. As I mentioned above, although there are problems in all areas of the language, the most serious difficulties are encountered in listening comprehension and in the students' expression of their thoughts, that is, speaking. Weaknesses in listening skills are undoubtedly related to the fact that students only have the opportunity to hear German words from their teachers and peers during class. Our ears are not used to foreign words because our mother tongue is used in the family, on the street and in other public places. Of course, in order to overcome this deficiency, Methodists put forward many methods and types of tasks. Babayev Javid notes in his article "Listening to native-speakers continuously, develops understanding the target language. Native speakers frequently address idioms, phrases, jargons, argots, proverbs, sayings which are characteristic for everyday colloquial speech mainly" [2, p. 14]. Hasan Alisoy underlines about the important of listening: "Language acquisition takes place in the following order: listening, then speaking. Language is first developed in a human as a receptive skill, and listening awakens awareness of that skill [7, p.44].

For the development of this field, not only at the university, but also at home, students should regularly

listen carefully and purposefully to CDs and other audio recordings, both prepared as teaching aids and other CDs [5], through headphones. It should not be forgotten that the negative sides of modern devices and applications may also distract the students in the process of lesson [6, p. 102]. It is very difficult to understand them when the material selected for is full of unknown words and phrases, grammatical rules [3], words with similar pronunciation. Therefore, at the beginning of teaching, students should be presented with materials related to a certain picture or situation. Reading material in a foreign language should not be fast, even at the beginning this speed should be lower than normal, but over time the speed is gradually increased. During listening, students should be able to visually understand the teacher's pronunciation, tempo, and intonation, otherwise, translating what they are thinking in Azerbaijani language into German will cause a pause in the speech, which cannot be called a perfect speech. Among the four basic skills and habits of the language, speech occupies the most important place, because students' grammatical knowledge, pronunciation skills, and vocabulary are related, and the intellectual level, logical thinking, and general outlook of each student are revealed through speech. In order for students to speak correctly, first of all, they should be told that while they speak at a normal speed, they should think about their speech or just their sentences and take short pauses, which will allow them to think on the one hand, and on the other hand, to understand and correct their mistakes. Sometimes, mother tongue is not used in language learning process which causes to big problems in just-beginners [4].

When we talk, we constantly imagine the person we are addressing and try to communicate clearly and successfully with him, we try to create interactive conditions to achieve this goal. Gestures, eye contact, facial expressions and other movements, tone of voice, harmony are very important tools for a person to express his thoughts in more detail, and it is necessary to try so that students use these tools skillfully. The development of speech is also related to its use in various types of text forms, that is, participating in a conversation, discussion, answering the phone, telling a story, addressing someone in a store or on the street, etc. The language skills, sentence structures, vocabulary, formal or informal language levels used in the cases are completely different from each other. In the interviews conducted for the development of speech in the book "Knowledge Test Teaching Course", teachers expressed different attitudes. For example: "Because my students are very embarrassed in front of their group mates because of their mistakes and slurred speech, I don't make them speak a foreign language in class." Another claims that the students make so much noise during the conversation that the teachers in the next room complain. But many teachers advise that students should be encouraged to talk to each other, while they are so interested in each other's opinion that they try to talk without stopping without realizing the mistakes they have made. I think that if a foreign language is taught, it is important to understand the importance and purpose of its teaching and to inculcate

it in students at the level of using this language as a practical means of communication.

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